

Complexes of Niobium Pentachloride with Primary, Mono and Diamine in Non-Polar Solvents

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The complexes of niobium pentachloride with α -naphthyl amine, β -naphthyl amine, *p*-anisidine, *p*-toluidine, *m*-toluidine, *o*-phenetidine, *m*-phenetidine, 3, 4-xylidine, aniline, *o*-toluidine, *p*-phenylene diamine have been prepared. In case of primary mono amines, the ratio of NbCl₅ and amines was found to be 1 : 3 and in case of diamines, the ratio of NbCl₅ and amines was 2 : 3.

SEVERAL kinds of complexes of niobium have been prepared and studied. Among them, bromo complexes of quinquevalent niobium¹, Nb(V) complexes² of amino poly carboxylic acids, complexes of Nb(IV) halides³, Nb-xylene orange complex⁴, Nb complexes⁵ of oxygen-18 labelled terminal and bridging monoxoniobium(V) complexes and crystalline Et₂O, NbCl₅ complexes⁶ are significant.

No detailed work on the formation of complexes of niobium pentachloride with amines and heterocyclic bases in non-aqueous media appears to have been reported in the literature. The present investigation was therefore undertaken with the view of studying the formation of the compounds of niobium pentachloride with amines in non-polar solvents and to study them in detail.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of B. D. H. or E. Merck 'extra pure' quality. Carbon tetrachloride and

ethylacetate were dried over calcium chloride for several days and distilled twice before use. Dehydrated samples of benzene and other reagents were used in the complex formation. Anhydrous niobium pentachloride (Fluka) was dissolved in carbon tetrachloride and the amines were dissolved separately in benzene. The complexes were prepared by adding an excess of the amine solution to that of the niobium pentachloride solution when a precipitate formed. The precipitate was filtered, washed free of the amine with carbon tetrachloride and benzene and dried in a desiccator. The experiments were carried out in a dry box to avoid moisture. Niobium and chlorine were estimated by Duma's method; carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen by micro-analytical methods at the chemical laboratories of Magadh University, Bodh-Gaya.

Results and Discussion

Some complexes of niobium(V) are coloured and some are white as indicated in Table 1. All are

TABLE 1—COMPLEXES WITH PRIMARY, MONO AND DIAMINES

Complexes	Colour	m.p.	%Nb Found (Calcd.)	%Cl Found (Calcd.)	%N ₂ Found (Calcd.)	%C Found (Calcd.)	%H ₂ Found (Calcd.)
1. Nb(C ₁₀ H ₇ NH ₂) ₃ Cl ₅	Violet	277°d	13.01 (13.29)	24.94 (25.37)	5.80 (6.00)	50.81 (51.45)	4.02 (3.86)
2. Nb(C ₁₀ H ₇ NH ₂) ₃ Cl ₅	White	272°d	13.02 (13.29)	25.19 (25.37)	5.95 (6.00)	51.30 (51.45)	4.03 (3.86)
3. Nb(C ₇ H ₅ ON) ₃ Cl ₅	White	225°	14.65 (14.54)	27.26 (27.75)	6.29 (6.56)	38.94 (39.40)	3.94 (4.22)
4. Nb(C ₇ H ₅ N) ₃ Cl ₅	White	270°d	15.91 (15.72)	30.05 (30.00)	6.89 (7.10)	42.83 (42.62)	4.58 (4.56)
5. Nb(C ₇ H ₅ N) ₃ Cl ₅	White	265°d	14.93 (15.72)	31.65 (30.00)	6.78 (7.10)	42.41 (42.62)	4.49 (4.56)
6. Nb(C ₈ H ₁₁ ON) ₃ Cl ₅	Violet	215°	13.88 (13.64)	20.34 (20.17)	6.21 (6.16)	42.44 (42.25)	4.78 (4.85)
7. Nb(C ₈ H ₁₁ ON) ₃ Cl ₅	Violet	217°	13.42 (13.64)	20.48 (20.17)	6.30 (6.16)	42.42 (42.25)	4.68 (4.85)
8. Nb(C ₈ H ₁₁ N) ₃ Cl ₅	White	265°d	14.48 (14.54)	27.61 (27.75)	6.68 (6.56)	44.32 (45.03)	— (6.09)
9. Nb(C ₈ H ₉ N) ₃ Cl ₅	White	265°d	15.98 (16.92)	32.50 (32.58)	7.62 (7.71)	39.75 (39.66)	3.76 (3.82)
10. Nb ₂ (C ₁₄ H ₁₆ N ₂) ₃ Cl ₁₀	Violet	255°d	15.84 (15.80)	30.14 (30.16)	7.16 (7.13)	42.85 (42.82)	— (4.07)
11. Nb ₂ (C ₈ H ₈ N ₂) ₃ Cl ₁₀	White	250°d	21.44 (21.50)	41.21 (41.04)	9.80 (9.71)	24.81 (24.97)	— (3.77)

d—decomposes.

TABLE 2—INFRARED SPECTRA DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

With β -naphthyl amine		With <i>p</i> -anisidine amine		With <i>p</i> -phenylene diamine	
Stretching frequency in cm^{-1}	Remarks	Stretching frequency in cm^{-1}	Remarks	Stretching frequency in cm^{-1}	Remarks
608 } 689 } 691 }	C-Cl stretch.	639 } 733 } 776 }	C-Cl stretch.	624 } 696 }	C-Cl stretch.
920	C-H bend in benzene ring.	920	C-H bend in benzene ring.	910	C-H bend in benzene ring.
1258 } 1300 }	C-N stretch.	1263	C-N stretch.	1300	C-N stretch.
1482	C-H bend in C=C-H	1404	C=C-H bend	1466	C-H bend in C=C-H
1388	-CH ₃ sym. bend	1326	-CH ₃ sym. bend	1398	-CH ₃ sym. bend
1549	N-H bend	1549	N-H bend		
		1040	-O-O-O stretch		
		1414	C-C- and C-O stretch		
2916	C-H or N-H stretch.	2896	C-H or O-H		
		2916	or N-H stretch.		
3479	NH ₂ bonded	3499	NH ₂ bonded	3468	NH ₂ bonded

crystalline solid and fairly stable in dry air at room temperature.

The complexes of niobium pentachloride formed with α -naphthyl amine, β -naphthyl amine, *p*-anisidine, *p*-toluidine, *m*-toluidine, *p*-anisidine, *o*-toluidine are insoluble in water whereas those formed with *o*-phenetidine, *m*-phenetidine, 3, 4-xylidine, *p*-phenylene diamine are soluble in water.

The complexes of niobium pentachloride with α -naphthyl amine, β -naphthyl amine, *o*-toluidine, aniline, *p*-phenylene diamine are insoluble in methanol, benzene and ethyl acetate.

Niobium pentachloride complexes with *p*-anisidine, *p*-toluidine, *m*-toluidine; 3, 4-xylidine, *o*-phenetidine, *m*-phenetidine are soluble in methanol, benzene and ethyl acetate. The complexes with α -naphthyl amine, β -naphthyl amine, aniline, *p*-phenylene diamine are soluble in con. H₂SO₄ whereas the remaining ones are soluble in HCl. They have high melting points, some of them decompose on heating.

Magnetic susceptibility of the complexes with β -naphthyl amine, *o*-phenetidine, *p*-anisidine, *p*-phenylene diamine were determined and all of them were found to be diamagnetic.

Infrared spectra : IR spectra of complexes with β -naphthyl amine, *p*-anisidine, *p*-phenylene diamine were recorded by the Perkin-Elmer Spectrophotometer in KBr phase in the range of 200 to 4000 cm^{-1} at Chemistry Department, Banaras Hindu University

and the frequencies of different complexes are shown in Table 2. In all the cases a strong and broad peak between 3400 cm^{-1} to 3500 cm^{-1} (stretching frequency of bonded aromatic primary amines)^{1,7} confirms the coordination of niobium through nitrogen of aromatic amine.

From the analytical data, the ratio of NbCl₅ : organic amines were found to be 1 : 3 in the case of a mono amines and 1 : 1.5 for a diamine.

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References

1. P. J. D. JONES, *J. Chem. Soc. A*, 1967, 247.
2. KONECNY CTIRAD, *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1969, 240, 196.
3. GERALD W. A. FOWLES and D. J. TIDMARSH, *Org. Nuclear Chem.*, 1969, 31, 2373.
4. BADRI VISHAL AGARWALA and ARUN K. DEY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, 44, 691.
5. VLADIMIR KATOVIC and GIRILA DJIRDJIVIC, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1970, 9, 1720.
6. ALAN COWLEY, FRED FAIRBROTHER and NORMAN SCOTT, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 3133.
7. JOHN R. DYER, "A Text Book of Application Absorption Spectroscopy of Organic Compounds", Prentice Hall of India Private Limited, New Delhi, 1979, p. 73.